

Can a Multi-Epitope Vaccine be a solution for COVID-19 pandemic?

Domina Petric

Introduction

Problems associated with Wuhan spike protein-based vaccines, which are BNT162b2 (Pfizer-BioNTech: mRNA vaccine), mRNA-1273 (Moderna: mRNA vaccine), Ad26.COVS.2.S (Janssen/Johnson & Johnson COVID-19 vaccine: replication-incompetent adenovirus 26 vector based vaccine that expresses a stabilized spike protein), ChAdOx1 nCoV19/AZD1222 (University of Oxford, AstraZeneca, and the Serum Institute of India: replication incompetent chimpanzee adenovirus vector based vaccine that expresses the spike protein), NVXCoV2373 (Novavax: recombinant protein nanoparticle vaccine composed of trimeric spike glycoproteins and a potent Matrix-M1 adjuvant), Ad5-based COVID19 vaccine (CanSino Biologics: replication-incompetent adenovirus 5 vector based vaccine that expresses the spike protein), Gam-COVID-Vac/Sputnik V (Gamaleya Institute: two replication incompetent adenovirus vectors that express a full-length spike glycoprotein) [1], are:

1. The emergence of new SARS-CoV-2 strains (spike protein-based mutations) that are more or less resistant to Wuhan spike protein-based vaccine-induced immunity.
2. Toxicity of the spike protein.

NEW SARS-CoV-2 STRAINS

According to World Health Organization [2] SARS-CoV-2 variant of concern (VOC) is one that is associated with one or more of the following:

1. Increase in transmissibility or detrimental change in COVID-19 epidemiology; OR
2. Increase in virulence or change in clinical disease presentation; OR
3. Decrease in effectiveness of public health and social measures or available diagnostics, vaccines, therapeutics.

VOC are:

1. Alpha (B.1.1.7; significant S protein amino acid mutations are +S: 484K and +S: 452R; United Kingdom)
2. Beta (B.1.351, B.1.351.2, B.1.351.3; +S: L18F; South Africa)
3. Gamma (P.1, P.1.1, P.1.2, P.1.4, P.1.6, P.1.7; +S: 681H; Brazil)
4. Delta (B.1.617.2, AY.1, AY.2, AY.3, AY.3.1; +S: 417N; India)

A SARS-CoV variant of interest (VOI) is one with genetic changes that can or will affect virus characteristics (transmissibility, disease severity, immune escape, diagnostic or therapeutic escape) and identified to cause significant community transmission or multiple COVID-19 clusters, in multiple countries with increasing relative prevalence alongside increasing number of cases over time, or other apparent 3 epidemiological impacts to suggest an emerging risk to global public health.

VOI are:

1. Eta (B.1.525, multiple countries)
2. Iota (B.1.526, United States of America)
3. Kappa (B.1.617.1, India)
4. Lambda (C.37, Peru)

The Delta Plus variant has $\geq 20\%$ significant number of high-prevalence mutations in comparison with the Delta variant. Signature mutations in S protein (which are G142D, A222V, and T95I) exist at a more significant percentage in comparison with the Delta variant. Three

mutations in S protein (K417N, V70F, and W258L) are exclusively present in the Delta Plus variant. A new mutation was identified in ORF1a (A1146T), which is only present in the Delta Plus variant with 58 % prevalence. Five key mutations (T95I, A222V, G142D, R158G, and K417N) are significantly more prevalent in the Delta Plus than in the Delta variant. These mutations weaken the immune response [3].

A novel variant of concern named CAL.20C (B.1.427/B.1.429) or epsilon variant (California) carries spike glycoprotein mutations S13I in the signal peptide, W152C in the N-terminal domain (NTD), and L452R in the receptor-binding domain (RBD). Plasma from individuals vaccinated with a Wuhan-1 isolate-based messenger RNA vaccine or from convalescent individuals exhibited neutralizing titers that were reduced 2- to 3.5- fold against the B.1.427/B.1.429 variant relative to wild-type pseudoviruses. The L452R mutation reduced neutralizing activity in 14 of 34 RBD-specific monoclonal antibodies (mAbs). The S13I and W152C mutations resulted in total loss of neutralization for 10 of 10 NTD-specific mAbs because the NTD antigenic supersite was remodeled by a shift of the signal peptide cleavage site and the formation of a new disulfide bond, as revealed by mass spectrometry and structural studies [4].

New COVID-19 variant of interest is called Mu. This variant is predicted to be able to evade both natural and vaccine-induced immunity. It is also known as B.1.621 variant. It was first identified in Colombia, and has now been detected in 43 countries so far [5].

NATURAL IMMUNITY

Gazit and coworkers concluded, based on the results of a retrospective observational study comparing SARS-CoV-2-naive individuals fully vaccinated with BioNTech/Pfizer mRNA BNT162b2 vaccine, previously infected not vaccinated individuals and previously infected single dose vaccinated individuals, that natural immunity confers longer lasting and stronger protection against infection, symptomatic disease and hospitalization caused by the Delta variant, compared to the BNT162b2 two-dose vaccine-induced immunity. Individuals who were both previously infected with SARS-CoV-2 and given a single dose of the vaccine gained additional protection against the Delta variant [6].

Shrestha and coworkers conducted a study evaluating the necessity of COVID-19 vaccination in individuals previously infected with SARS-CoV-2 and concluded that previously infected individuals are unlikely to benefit from COVID-19 vaccination. It is important to prioritize COVID-19 vaccines to SARS-CoV-2-naive individuals [7]. It seems that, based on these findings, epitope-rich broad-spectrum natural immunity provides longer lasting and stronger protection against new SARS-CoV-2 strains than the Wuhan spike-based vaccine-

induced narrow immunity.

TOXICITY OF THE SPIKE PROTEIN

Available vaccines based on the Wuhan spike protein can be associated with rare, but serious side effects that must be monitored closely. Serious side effects reported with Janssen COVID-19 vaccine are capillary leak syndrome, cerebral venous sinus thrombosis, deep venous thrombosis including pulmonary embolism, thrombocytopenia, transverse sinus thrombosis with thrombocytopenia, anaphylaxis, Guillain-Barré syndrome, seizures and vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia. Similar side effects were also reported with AstraZeneca/Oxford COVID-19 vaccine (vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia, deep venous thrombosis, capillary leak syndrome, cerebral venous sinus thrombosis). Serious side effects reported with mRNA Pfizer and Moderna vaccines are myocarditis, pericarditis and anaphylaxis [8].

A case report of a right peroneal and popliteal vein phlebothrombosis, that occurred shortly after the second dose of mRNA (Pfizer/BioNTech) vaccine was published by Carli and coworkers. Authors concluded that the intense second dose-induced immunological response might act as a trigger for deep venous thrombosis [9]. Another clinical report of a 59-year-old woman presented to the Emergency Department with a 3-day history of sudden-onset left leg pain 7 days after receiving her first dose of mRNA vaccine (Pfizer/BioNTech) was published. The patient was diagnosed with deep vein thrombosis and pulmonary embolism. Authors concluded that there could be a link between vaccination and thrombotic event [10].

SARS-CoV-2 infection starts with the binding of S protein to ACE (angiotensin-converting enzyme) 2 in the host cells. Vascular endothelium can be infected by SARS-CoV-2, which triggers mitochondrial reactive oxygen species production and glycolytic shift. In a study, researchers showed that S protein alone can damage vascular endothelial cells (ECs) by down-regulating ACE2 and consequently inhibiting mitochondrial function. A pseudovirus expressing S protein (PseuSpike) was administered to Syrian hamsters intratracheally. Lung damage was apparent in animals receiving Pseu-Spike, revealed by thickening of the alveolar septa and increased infiltration of mononuclear cells. Although the use of a noninfectious pseudovirus is a limitation to this study, the data of this study reveal that S protein alone can damage endothelium [11].

In another study researchers investigated the toxicity of spike protein in vitro using endothelial cell culture and recombinant SARS-CoV-2 spike protein S1 Receptor Binding Domain (Spike). Mouse brain microvascular endothelial cells from normal (C57BL/6 mice) and diabetic (db/db) mice were used. An endothelial transwell permeability assay revealed

increased permeability in diabetic cells as well as after Spike treatment. The expression of VE-Cadherin, an endothelial adherens junction protein, JAM-A, a tight junctional protein, Connexin-43, a gap junctional protein, and PECAM-1, were all decreased significantly after Spike treatment in control and to a greater extent, in diabetic cells. In control cells, Spike treatment increased association of endothelial junctional proteins with Rab5a, a mediator of the endocytic trafficking compartment. In cerebral arteries isolated from control and diabetic animals, Spike protein had a greater effect in down regulating expression of endothelial junctional proteins in arteries from diabetic animals than from control animals. Authors concluded that Spike-induced degradation of endothelial junctional proteins affects endothelial barrier function and is the likely cause of vascular damage observed in COVID-19 affected individuals [12].

Høeg and coworkers concluded in their study, which was designed for the establishment of the rate of post-vaccination cardiac myocarditis in the 12-15 and 16-17-year-old population in the context of their COVID-19 hospitalization risk, that post-vaccination stratified cardiac adverse event (mRNA vaccine-related myocarditis) rate was highest in young boys aged 12-15 following dose two. The incidence exceeds their expected 120-day COVID-19 hospitalization rate [13].

ANTIBODY DEPENDENT ENHANCEMENT

Virus-specific antibodies are considered antiviral and play an important role in the control of virus infections in a number of ways, but sometimes the presence of specific antibodies can be beneficial to the virus. This activity is known as antibody-dependent enhancement (ADE) of virus infection. The ADE of virus infection is a phenomenon in which virus-specific antibodies enhance the entry of virus, and in some cases the replication of virus, into monocytes/macrophages and granulocytic cells through interaction with Fc and/or complement receptors [14].

ADE may occur in people receiving vaccines based on the original Wuhan strain spike sequence (either mRNA or viral vectors) and then exposed to a Delta variant [15]. COVID-19 vaccines designed to elicit neutralizing antibodies may sensitize vaccine recipients to more severe disease than if they were not vaccinated [16].

MULTI-EPI TOPE VACCINE

All structural proteins of SARS-CoV-2 can be used as vaccine candidates. N protein is associated with replicase-transcriptase complexes and is involved with the packaging, transcription,

and replication of the virus. N protein stimulates potent antibodies, which in turn may trigger cytokine production. Open reading frame 3a (ORF3a) is also essential for viral replication and virulence of SARS-CoV. ORF3a's function is to stimulate pro-IL-1 β gene expression and IL-1 β secretion that affect the lungs severely [17].

A study has been published in the Journal of Biomolecular Structure and Dynamics which focuses on the evaluation of E, M, N, ORF10, ORF8, ORF3a, and M proteins 6 using bioinformatics tools to develop a multi-epitope COVID-19 vaccine. In this study, bioinformatics approaches were employed to design and introduce a novel multi-epitope vaccine against 2019-nCoV that can potentially trigger both CD4+ and CD8+ T-cell immune responses and investigated its biological activities by computational tools. Three known antigenic proteins (Nucleocapsid, ORF3a, and Membrane protein, hereafter called NOM) from the virus were selected and analyzed for prediction of the potential immunogenic B and T-cell epitopes and then validated using bioinformatics tools. Based on in silico analysis, the researchers have constructed a multi-epitope vaccine candidate (NOM) with five rich-epitopes domain including highly scored T and B-cell epitopes. After predicting and evaluating of the third structure of the protein candidate, the best 3D predicted model was applied for docking studies with Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4) and HLA-A*11:01. In the next step, molecular dynamics (MD) simulation was used to evaluate the stability of the designed fusion protein with TLR4 and HLA-A*11:01 receptors. MD studies demonstrated that the NOM-TLR4 and NOM-HLA-A*11:01 docked models were stable during simulation time. In silico evaluation showed that the designed chimeric protein could simultaneously elicit humoral and cell-mediated immune responses [18].

CONCLUSION

Problems associated with Wuhan spike protein-based vaccines are the emergence of new SARS-CoV-2 strains that are more or less resistant to Wuhan spike protein-based vaccine-induced immunity, and toxicity of the spike protein (S protein alone can damage vascular endothelial cells). All structural proteins of SARS-CoV-2 can be used as vaccine candidates (such as E, M, N, ORF3a, and M proteins). Multi-epitope vaccine could recognize and assemble B and T-cell epitopes that could efficiently trigger and elicit multi-epitope immunity against SARS-CoV-2, that could also be more efficient against new strains than the Wuhan spike protein-based narrow immunity. Multi-epitope vaccine against SARS-CoV-2, excluding the spike protein, could potentially be less toxic than Wuhan spike protein-based vaccines, with less serious side effects, but still enough immunogenic to elicit protective immune response. Another potential benefit of a multi-epitope COVID-19 vaccine is that, taking into

account the fact that most of the new SARS-CoV-2 strains carry significant new mutations in the spike protein and less significant mutations in other structural proteins of the virus, it could provide more potent immune response against new strains. Spike-protein might not be an Achilles tendon of the virus. It is worth investing money and effort to find one or more epitopes that could be the Achilles tendon. Vaccination is important both on the individual and on the population level. Individual benefit from the vaccination is a reduction of the risk for symptomatic, especially severe COVID-19, permanent consequences and death. Population benefit is reducing the transmission of the virus, repression of the virus and finally, disabling the virus from the gain-of-function mutations, and inducing loss-of-function mutations. Pandemic is now developing in the gain-of-function direction, and it would be beneficial to change the course of the pandemic in the loss-of-function direction. Epitope-rich vaccine could be that factor that will change the course of the pandemic, but more preclinical and clinical research is mandatory.

References

- [1] Edwards KM, Orenstein WA. COVID-19: Vaccines to prevent SARS-CoV-2 infection. Hirsch MS, Bloom A, ed. UpToDate. Waltham, MA: UpToDate Inc. <https://www.uptodate.com> (Accessed on August 22, 2021.)
- [2] Tracking SARS-CoV-2 variants. Available at <https://www.who.int/en/activities/trackingSARS-CoV-2-variants/> (Accessed on August 22, 2021)
- [3] Kannan SR, Spratt AN, Cohen AR, et al. Evolutionary analysis of the Delta and Delta Plus variants of the SARS-CoV-2 viruses. *J Autoimmun.* 2021;124: 102715.
- [4] McCallum M, Bassi J, Marco A, et al. SARSCoV-2 immune evasion by variant B.1.427/B.1.429. *bioRxiv* [Preprint]. 2021 Apr 1:2021.03.31.437925. doi: 10.1101/2021.03.31.437925.
- [5] Crist C. WHO Tracking New COVID-19 Variant Called Mu. Available at <https://www.webmd.com/lung/news/20210902/who-tracking-new-covid-variant-called-mu> (Accessed on September 6, 2021)
- [6] Gazit S, Shlezinger R, Perez G, et al. Comparing SARS-CoV-2 natural immunity to vaccine-induced immunity: reinfections versus breakthrough infections. *medRxiv.* August 25, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.08.24.21262415>
- [7] Shrestha NK, Burke PC, Nowacki AS, et al. Necessity of COVID-19 vaccination in previously infected individuals. *medRxiv.* June 05, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.06.01.21258176>
- [8] Micromedex® (electronic version). IBM Watson Health, Greenwood Village, Colorado, USA. Available at: <https://www.micromedexsolutions.com/> (cited: August/22/2021).
- [9] Carli G, Nichele I, Ruggeri M, et al. Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) occurring shortly after the second dose of mRNA SARS-CoV2 vaccine. *Intern Emerg Med.* 2021;16(3):803-804.
- [10] Al-Maqbali JS, Al Rasbi S, Kashoub MS, et al. A 59-Year-Old Woman with Extensive Deep Vein Thrombosis and Pulmonary Thromboembolism 7 Days Following a First Dose of the Pfizer-BioNTech BNT162b2 mRNA COVID-19 Vaccine. *Am J Case Rep.* 2021;22: e932946.
- [11] Yuyang L, Zhang J, Schiavon CR, et al. SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein Impairs Endothelial Function via Downregulation of ACE 2. *Circ. Res.* 2021; 128:1323-1326.

- [12] Raghavan S, Kenchappa DB, Leo MD. SARS-CoV-2 Spike Protein Induced Degradation of Junctional Proteins That Maintain Endothelial Barrier Integrity. *Front. Cardiovasc. Med.* 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcvm.2021.687783>
- [13] Høeg TB, Krug A, Stevenson J, Mandrola J. SARS-CoV-2 mRNA Vaccination-Associated Myocarditis in Children ages 12-17: A Stratified National Database Analysis. *medRxiv*, September 08, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.08.30.21262866>
- [14] Tirado SM, Yoon KJ. Antibody-dependent enhancement of virus infection and disease. *Viral Immunol.* 2003;16(1):69-86.
- [15] Yahi N, Chahinian H, Fantini J. Infection-enhancing anti-SARS-CoV-2 antibodies recognize both the original Wuhan/D614G strain and Delta variants. A potential risk for mass vaccination? *J. Infect.* 2021.
- [16] Cardozo T, Veazey R. Informed consent disclosure to vaccine trial subjects of risk of COVID-19 vaccines worsening clinical disease. *Int J Clin Pract.* 2021;75(3):e13795.
- [17] Bose P. A novel multi-epitope COVID-19 vaccine developed using reverse vaccinology. Available at <https://www.newsmedical.net/news/20210531/A-novel-multiepitope-COVID-19-vaccine-developed-using-reverse-vaccinology.aspx> (Accessed on August 22, 2021)
- [18] Enayatkhani M, Hasaniazad M, Faezi S, et al. Reverse vaccinology approach to design a novel multi-epitope vaccine candidate against COVID-19: an in-silico study. *J Biomol Struct Dyn.* 2020;39(8):2857-2872.